

A Study on 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-chloropyrazole-4-carboxaldehyde. Synthesis of fused Pyrazole, Isoxazole, Pyrimidine and Pyridine-[2,3-*d*]pyrazoline Derivatives

FAWI M. ABD EL-LATIF

Chemistry Department, Aswan Faculty of Science, Aswan, Egypt

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In spite of the literature reported on the chemistry of pyrazole nucleus¹, no attention has been paid to the chemistry of 4-carboxaldehyde-5-chloropyrazole², although it should be an excellent starting material for synthesis of many fused heteropyrazole derivatives. Several pyridines, pyrazolines and pyrimidines are known as herbicides³. The present communication reports the synthesis of different heterocyclic compounds which may have potential herbicidal activity.

Results and Discussion

The aldehydic compound (1) reacted with α -cyanoacetamide, α -cyanothioacetamide and cyanoacetohydrazide to afford the condensation products 2, 3 and 4 respectively. Refluxing each of 2, 3 or 4 in pyridine yielded 5, 6 and 7 respectively.

The reactivity of the aldehydic group prompted us to investigate the condensation reactions with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Actually, the use of basic catalyst, refluxing time as well as the attacking reagents play a role in the nature of the condensation products—cyclic or acyclic. Piperidine catalysed reaction of 1 with hydrazine hydrate resulted in a yellow precipitate. The elemental analysis, ¹Hnmr and mass spectra indicated the cyclic structure (10), obtained as the hydrochloride salt. The filtrate on dilution with water afforded a yellow fine precipitate which showed acyclic structure (8). Compounds 8 and 9 have been isolated using

triethylamine as a catalyst even under long refluxing, whereas using piperidine produced compound 11

in low yield. Fusion of compounds **8** and **9** in pyridine afforded compounds **10** and **11** respectively.

Reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride with compound **1** did not proceed in triethylamine. However, use of catalytic amount of piperidine or sodium hydroxide produced the same isoxazole (**12**). Formation of the pyrimidine nucleus upon several α,β -unsaturated ketonic system has been described.⁴ Pyrazolopyridine derivatives (**13**, **14**) have been obtained using alcoholic sodium hydroxide.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Elemental analyses and ir spectra (KBr; recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 127 B spectrophotometer) were carried out at Micro-analytical Center, Cairo University. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were obtained on a Varian EM 360 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra (MAT 311 A, 70 eV) at Duisburg University, Germany. All the reaction were followed by tlc. All compounds gave satisfactory microanalytical results for N and Cl.

5-Chloro-3-methyl-4-(cyanoacetamido)-1-phenylpyrazolines (2-4) : A mixture of equimolar amounts (0.01 mol) of **1** and α -cyanoacetamide, α -cyanothioacetamide or cyanoacetohydrazide respectively, were dissolved in ethanol (40 ml), and catalytic amount of triethylamine was refluxed for 4-6 h, then filtered, concentrated and diluted with cold water. The resultant solids were crystallised from proper solvent, (yields 60-85%) : **2**, m.p. 172°, ν_{\max} 1 725 (C=O), 2 210 (CN), 3 500-3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.3 (3H, s, Me), 2.8 (2H, br, NH₂), 6.8 (1H, s, CH), 7.2-7.6 (5H, m, ArH); **3**, 180°, ν_{\max} 1 200 (C=S), 2 220 (CN), 3 500-3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.3 (3H, s, Me) 2.8 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.7 (1H, s, CH), 6.9-7.3 (5H, m, ArH); **4**, 205°.

5-Cyano-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazolo[2,3-d]pyridin-6-ones (5-7) : Compounds **2-4** were fused in pyridine (15 ml), refluxed for 2 h at 120-40°, cooled, evaporated under reduced pressure till dry-

ness. It was then extracted with ethanol whereby brownish precipitates were produced on addition of a few drops of water and then crystallised from ethanol to yield the products (yields 55-70%) : **5**, m.p. 190°, ν_{\max} 1 710 (C=O), 2 220 (CN), 3 340 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.2 (3H, s, Me), 7.1-7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, pyridine), 11.2 (1H, s, NH); **6**, 195°; **7**, 238°.

5-Chloro-3-methyl-4-(methylhydrazino)-1-phenylpyrazolines (8, 9) : To ethanolic solution of **1** (0.01 mol), an excess of hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine (0.015 mol) was added, triethylamine was added as catalyst and refluxed for 10 h. It was then filtered, concentrated and cooled. The resulting yellowish solids were crystallised from methanol to yield the products (yields 65-70%) : **8**, m.p.178°; **9**, 150°, ν_{\max} 1 620 (C=C), 3 500- 3 330 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); δ 1.2 (3H, s, Me), 3.8 (2H, br, NH₂), 5.9 (1H, s, CH), 7.2-7.5 (5H, m, ArH).

3-Methyl-1-phenylpyrazol[2,3-d]pyrazolines and/or -isoxazolines (10-12) : A mixture of **8/9** and pyridine (15 ml) was refluxed for 4-6 h, then evaporated till dryness, extracted with ethanol, cooled, filtered and the resulting solids were crystallised from methanol (yields 55-60%) : **10**, m.p. 235°; **11**, 135°, ν_{\max} 1 620 (C=C), 3 470- 3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.3 (3H, s, Me), 5.6 (1H, s, CH), 7.2-7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 11.2 (1H, br, NH); **12**, 95°.

3-Methyl-1-phenylpyrazol[2,3-d]-1,4-di(H)-pyrimidin-6-ones (13, 14) : Alcoholic solution of **1** (0.01 mol) and urea or thiourea (0.02 mol) in presence of 3 N NaOH was refluxed for 15 h on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was then filtered hot and cooled. The solid separated upon adding dilute HCl was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (yield 60%) : **13**, m.p. 180°, ν_{\max} 1 540 (C=N), 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 1.2 (3H, s, Me), 5.8 (1H, s, CH), 7.2-7.5 (5H, m, ArH); **14**, 120°, ν_{\max} 1 620 (C=N) 3 500- 3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.2 (3H, s, Me), 7.3-7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, s, H-4-pyrimidine), 10.2 (1H, br, NH).

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